

Multi-matrix continuously-reinforced composites for waste reduction and repair applications

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ICCM23 Belfast

4th August 2023

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Growing Composite Waste

[1] Lefevre, A., *et al.* (2019). Anticipating in-use stocks of carbon fibre reinforced polymers and related waste generated by the wind power sector until 2050. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 141, 30–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.10.008>

Current Composite Repair

[2] Lkovaivos - <https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/4/46/Figure-4-typical-laminate-and-sandwich-repairs.jpg>

Current Composite Repair

[3]

[4]

[3] White, S., *et al.* Autonomic healing of polymer composites. *Nature* 409, 794–797 (2001).

[4] Pulikkalparambil H, *et al.* Self-repairing hollow-fiber polymer composites. *Self-Healing Composite Materials: From Design to Applications* 2020:313–26.

Ideal Composite Repair

- Want continuously reinforced repairs

- Want full fiber volume fraction

Multi-Matrix Continuously-Reinforce Composite (MMCRC)

Where could this be useful?

Locations where damage is expected:

- Leading edges of blades
- Contact/friction surfaces
- Damage susceptible corners of containers
- Likely impact locations
- Etc.

Leading Edge Erosion: Why We Keep Failing To Solve It (weatherguardwind.com)

When Your Luggage Arrives Damaged | BudgetAir.co.uk Blog

Carbon Fiber Brakes: An In-Depth Look With Strange Engineering - Dragzine

Vitrimers

- + Strong mechanical ability
- + Gentle reforming conditions
- + Improved resilience in varied environments
- + Can be reformed and recycled

Can vitrimer-based resin composites sufficiently repair interlaminar failures?

[5] Mallinda - <https://mallinda.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/what-are-vitrimers-presentation-2021.pdf>

Manufacturing

105 °C
~20 Bar

Testing

D6415/D6415M – 06a (2013)

FIG. 1 Test Specimen Geometry (SI units)

Manufacturing Issues, Part 1

Manufacturing Issues, Part 2

Repair

Oven Heal

- 1 or 2 hours, depending on samples at 110 °C.
- Under vacuum pressure.

Induction Healing

- 2 hours heated and under vacuum.
- Temperature maintained between 100 and 135 °C on all thermocouples.

Oven Repair Performance

1 Hours @ 110 °C
in Oven

2 hours @ 110 °C In
Oven

Induction Repair Performance

2 hours @ 100-135 °C
with Induction

Thank you

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We would like to thank Mallinda for the supply of their vitrimer

